

ISic0349

I.Sicily inscription 0349

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR141174

1. D (is) M (anibus) s (acrum)

2. T (itus) F(--- Foen

3. ix vixit

4. annis XXX

5. ES IS P V

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491558

EDR 141174

EDCS 21900387

Bibliography

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cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.61
Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae
Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus
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